

Time Management: An Effective Tools for Academic Staff On Their Job Performance in Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti, Ekiti State

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study is to examine how academic staff in the College of Education manage their time with their performance on their job. The University runs a collegian system, in which the College of Education is one of the Colleges in the University. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to help the study. The study was hinged on ABC System theory. This study adopted descriptive research of the survey type. The population for the study consisted of all academic's staff in the college of education, a total of 158, the sample of the study made up of 68 academic staff using a random sampling technique. A validated questionnaire was used to elicit information. The split half method was used to test the reliability of the instrument. It was revealed that academic staff maximized their time and judiciously utilize it for effective job performance in the institution, and also male lecturers were able to maximize their time for effective job performance more than female lecturers. It is recommended that there is need for urgent training and re-training of academic staff especially the female ones on how to effectively manage time such that their work efficiency in the school will not be hampered.

Keywords: Time Management, Academic staff, Work Efficiency and Job performance,

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Introduction

Time Management is the process of planning and exercising conscious control of time spent on specific activities especially to increase effectiveness, efficiency, and productivity. Good management enables an individual to complete more in a shorter period of time, lowers stress and leads to career success (Wikipedia, 2020). Time management refers to making the best possible use of time (Prachi, 2020). Effective time management allows individuals to assign specific time slots to activities as per their importance. Time is the best use of time as time is always limited. Time management plays a very important role not only in organizations but also in our personal lives. Using time effectively gives the person "choice" on spending/managing activities at their own time and expediency. Time can be tricky and it is important to know how to fit work and daily activities into it (Kate, 2021). Managing time will allow one to have space to be creative and proactive with goals. Good time management leads to improved efficiency and productivity, less stress, and more success in life. Time management is very important for human being and organizations and it is a precious asset for achieving desired performance and accomplished duties (Faraj, 2023)

Some benefits of time management are, delivering work on time, providing a better quality of work, more productivity and efficiency, much less procrastination, less stress and anxiety, improved quality of life, more opportunities and career growth and more time for leisure and recreation (Niclas, 2020). The purpose of this study is to examine how academic staff in College of Education manages their time with their performance on their job.

Research Questions

1. What are the perspectives of academic staff on time management as a tool for effective job performance?
2. To what extent does time management affect academic staff on their job performance?

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between time management and job performance

Ho2: There is no significant difference between the effect of time management on male and female academic staff in their job performance

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive research of the survey type. The population for the study consisted of all academic's staff in college of education, a total 158, the sample of the study made up of 68 academic staff using random sampling technique. A questionnaire entitled 'Time Management' was used, the questionnaire has two sections, section A and B. it was rated using a four point likert scale. Time management questionnaire was developed by Peter Haddon (2010) with 50 items and was adapted for this study. For validity, the instrument was given to an expert for face and construct validity. Unnecessary contents were removed and corrections were done. For reliability, split half method was used to test the reliability of the instrument. The researcher administered the instrument, and was retrieved immediately after filling. The data generated for the study was analysed using Chi Square at 0.05 level of significance, t-test was used to analysed hypotheses two.

Results and Discussions

Question 1: What are the perspectives of academic staff on time management as a tool for effective job performance?

Table 1: Perspectives of academic staff on time management as a tool for effective job performance

S/N	Items	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
1.	I have up-to-date written goals for all areas of my life	3.25	0.94	Agreed
2.	I do compile and prioritize a written daily "To-Do" list	3.14	0.80	Agreed
3.	I do complete all items on my daily "To-Do" list	3.00	0.74	Agreed
4.	I do set and review my weekly objectives and success	3.07	0.78	Agreed
5.	I do set deadlines for my activities	3.17	0.81	Agreed
6.	All the daily activities I perform take me closer to my major goals	2.99	0.76	Agreed
7.	I meet up with deadlines for result submission	2.96	0.66	Agreed
8.	I easily combine religious with academic activities	3.22	0.65	Disagreed
9.	My daily lectures affect writing of papers in journals	2.00	0.78	Disagreed
10.	I have enough time to attend conferences	2.10	0.56	Disagreed
11.	I do believe that today is the only time to act	2.66	0.23	Agreed
12.	I do take action to minimize interruption or intrusions on my time	3.11	0.54	Agreed
13.	I am able to ensure uninterrupted periods for lectures	3.76	1.06	Agreed
14.	I consciously avoid making social telephone calls during lecture hours	2.77	1.11	Agreed
15.	I rarely procrastinate	2.90	0.76	Agreed
16.	I am usually 10 to 15 minutes early for all appointment	3.40	0.94	Agreed
17.	I am aware of and do make use of my creative periods daily	3.08	0.69	Agreed
18.	I do have unmarked assignment pile up	1.28	0.37	Agreed
19.	I usually visit people in their offices during office hour	1.08	0.39	Disagreed
20.	I do take measures to prevent telephone interruptions when attending to students	3.24	0.90	Agreed
21.	I do schedule time for physical exercise at least four time per week	2.66	0.23	Agreed
22.	I am able to relax in my free time without worrying about work	3.11	0.54	Agreed
23.	Students know the best time to reach me	2.76	0.66	Agreed
24.	I usually start and finish up the semester work with my students	3.22	0.82	Agreed
25.	I avoid taking work home	1.94	0.36	Disagreed
26.	I avoid staying late at the office to finish work	2.99	0.23	Agreed
27.	I usually take steps to avoid time-wasting activities	3.06	0.23	Agreed
28.	I have sufficient time available to spend on myself, family, community affairs and recreational/sporting activities	3.11	0.54	Agreed
Cluster Mean		2.82	0.47	Agreed

Source: Author Computation

The result presented in Table 1 revealed the perspectives of academic staff on time management as a tool for effective job performance. The majority of the respondents agreed with statements in items 1-7, 11-18, 20-24, and 26-28 as their mean values were greater than 2.50 decision level. However, item 8-10, 19, and 25 were disagreed. The decision level of 2.50

is got from the sum of the rating scale of four Likert scales in the questionnaire (i.e, SA – 4, A – 3, D – 2, and SD – 1) divided by four ($\frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = 2.50$). More so, the cluster means of 2.82 in the table was also greater than 2.50 which indicated that academic staff maximized time and judiciously utilize it for effective job performance in the institution.

Question 2: To what extent does time management affect academic staff on their job performance?

In analyzing the question, responses from time management were computed. To determine the extent of the effect of time management on academic staff's job performance, the respondents were categorized into "high", "moderate" and "low" extent. In the questionnaire, "High extent" was determined by adding the standard deviation to the mean ($2.82 + 0.47 = 3.29$), and "Low extent" is determined by subtracting the standard deviation from the mean response ($2.82 - 0.47 = 2.35$). "Moderate Extent" is the value of the mean response (2.82).

The extent of the effect of time management on academic staff's job performance is in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Extent of effect of time management on academic staff job performance

Extent of effect	Frequency	Percentage
High	24	35.3%
Moderate	40	58.8%
Low	4	5.9%
Total	68	100%

Source: Author Computation

The results of the analysis presented in Table 2 revealed that 35.3% of the respondents indicated that the effect of time management on their job performance was high, 58.8% indicated moderate and 5.9% of the respondents indicated low. This implies that there was a moderate effect of time management on academic staff job performance in the College of Education.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between time management and job performance

Table 3: Chi-Square test for relationship between time management and job performance

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Table	Exact Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20.411 ^a	1	.000	3.84	.000
Continuity Correction ^b	18.883	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	33.002	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test					
Linear-by-Linear Association	20.354	1	.000		

N of Valid Cases^b 68

Source: Author Computation

The result of analysis presented in Table 5 revealed that chi-square (X^2) calculated (20.411) was greater than chi-square table value of 3.84. Also, the P-value (0.000) was less than 0.05 level of significance. These results led to the rejection of the hypothesis. This means that there was a significant relationship between time management and job performance.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the effect of time management on male and female academic staff in their job performance

Table 4: t-test statistics for the difference between the effect of time management on male and female academic staff in their job performance

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	t-tab
Male	30	3.56	1.30	66	3.09	1.96
Female	38	3.01	1.65			

P < 0.05

The result of the analysis presented in Table 4 revealed that t-calculated (3.09) was greater than t-table (1.96) at a 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there was a significant difference between the effect of time management on male and female academic staff in their job performance. The male academic staff were found to efficiently manage their time for improved job performance than their female lecturers.

Discussions

The finding of this study revealed the perspectives of academic staff on time management as a tool for effective job performance. It was revealed that academic staff maximized their time and judiciously utilize it for effective job performance in the institution. The study showed that lecturers efficiently manage their time to have up-to-date written goals for all areas of their life, they compile and prioritize a written daily "To-Do" list, they do complete all items on their daily "To-Do" list, they set and review weekly objectives and success, they meet up with deadlines for result submission, despite their busy schedule in the school, they still have enough time to attend conferences, they do take action to minimize interruption or intrusions on their time, they rarely procrastinate, they usually arrive 10 to 15 minutes early for all appointment, they usually start and finish up the semester work with their students, they usually take steps to avoid time-wasting activities, they have sufficient time available to spend on themselves, family, community affairs and recreational/sporting activities. Abdullah, Mahmoud, and Omar (2012) stated that time is the most precious resource in business and society, unlike alternative resources, like labor and capital. However, few organizations really know how their time is an important resource. Time management helps improve employee's productivity, makes jobs easier, employees will perform tasks efficiently, helps employees attain the necessary tasks, and finally to record and guide the organization toward achieving its goals

The extent of the effect of time management on academic staff's job performance was also revealed in the study. The study showed that time management has moderate and a positive effect on academic staff's job performance in the College of Education. This means that there was a statistically significant relationship between time management and lecturers' job

performance. However, the positive effect of time management was higher on male academic staff than their female counterparts. This means that male academic staff are able to maximize their time for effective job performance more than female lecturers.

Conclusion

This study investigated Time Management: An Effective Tool for academic staff on their Job Performance in the College of Education, it was revealed that academic staff maximized their time and judiciously utilize it for effective job performance in the institution. The study showed that academic staff efficiently manage their time to have up-to-date written goals for all areas of their life. Based on the finding of this study, it was concluded that time management is a virile tool for lecturers' effectiveness and improved job performance in the College of Education, Ikere-Ekiti.

It is recommended that there is a need for urgent training and re-training of academic staff especially the female ones on how to effectively manage time such that their work efficiency in the school will not be hampered. The implications on their job are poor workflow, Poor time management results in wasted time, poor quality of work, and poor reputation.

References

- Abdullah, N.A., Mahmoud, K.A., & Omar, R.M. (2012). *Relationship between time management and job performance in Malaysia privet University*. Retrieved from www.researchgate.net/publication.
- Allan, L. (1973). *How to get control of your time and your life*. <https://books.google.com><about.
- Corporate Finance Institute (2020). *Tips for effective time management*, Retrieved from <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com>
- Faraj, H. (2023). *The effects of time management strategies on employee's performance efficiency*. Retrieved from Jordanan films
- Indeed, Career Guide (2018). *Time management skills, definition, and examples*. Retrieved from <https://www.indeed.com.time> management.
- Hanne, K. (2023) *Key to time management skills and how to improve them*. <https://www.ineed.com>
- Jennifer, H (2023). *10 ways to boost your professional time management skills*. [indeed.com/career](https://www.indeed.com/career). Advice/career- development/improved time management.
- Kate, K. (2021). *15 most effective and proven time management techniques*. Retrieved from [https:// www.timecamp.com](https://www.timecamp.com).
- Peter,H. (2010). *Time management questionnaire top achievers*, <https://www.stuou.com>>document.
- Prachi, J. (2020). *The Role of Time Management*, Retrieved from timemanagementstudy.guide.com.
- Niclas, M. (2020). *Benefits of Time Management*, Retrieved from [https:// www.mindtools.com.article](https://www.mindtools.com.article).
- Wikipedia (2020). www.wikipedia.com

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